

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF LEADER ACCOUNTABILITY ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TRANSCENDENTAL LEADERSHIP OF SCHOOL HEADS AND TEACHER SELF- EFFICACY

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Abstract: This study investigated the mediating influence of leader accountability on the relationship between transcendental leadership of school heads and teacher self-efficacy in public secondary schools in two municipalities of Davao Oriental. (Failure of teachers to maintain and improve their own performance in the classroom can have a significant impact on the students' learning. The ineffectiveness of teachers has an influence on the entire educational system. Teachers that are inept will have a detrimental influence on student learning results. Self-efficacy relates to one's belief in one's own skills and inefficiencies, which may lead to a number of psychological issues such as low confidence and low self-esteem). A stratified random sample approach was adopted, with 300 teachers serving as respondents. The findings of a non-experimental quantitative mediation study using medgraph, a validated questionnaire, mean, regression procedures, and Pearson r revealed substantial correlations between school leaders' transcendental leadership, teacher self-efficacy, and leader accountability. The mediating influence of leader accountability on the relationship between school leaders' transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy was partial. As a result, one of the ways that transcendental leadership of school heads may influence teacher self-efficacy is through leader accountability. However, this does not fully explain the relationship between the two variables.

Keywords: Transcendental Leadership; Teacher Self-efficacy; Leader Accountability; Mediating Effect; Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Failure of teachers to maintain and improve their own performance in the classroom can have a significant impact on the students' learning. The ineffectiveness of teachers has an influence on the entire educational system. Teachers that are inept will have a detrimental influence on student learning results. Self-efficacy relates to one's belief in one's own skills and inefficiencies, which may lead to a number of psychological issues such as low confidence and low self-esteem. In terms of teachers' efficacy, many schools are experiencing a teacher shortage. Most teachers do not put their expertise to good use in the classroom, notwithstanding low teacher performance. Furthermore, considerable research has indicated that teachers with low levels of self-efficacy have poorer job satisfaction, more work-related stress, and more difficulties dealing with students' disruptive behavior (Barni, Danioni, & Benevene, 2019; Shahzad & Naureen, 2017).

Relatively, developing teachers' self-efficacy is important. A more successful teacher is one who takes risks in the classroom and introduces higher requirements, which leads to improved student achievement. In a larger sense, teacher self-efficacy has been shown to be linked to other qualities such as work satisfaction, perfectionism, and emotional intelligence. The influence of teacher self-efficacy level on education and student learning outcomes is significant. Teacher effectiveness has an effect on students' academic progress in school (Alibakhshi, Nikdel, & Labbafi, 2020; Bal-Taştan, 2018).

On the other hand, there have been several attempts at conceptualization (Luthans, Luthans, Hodgetts, & Luthans, 2002; McCormick, 2001) and through research (Chemers, Watson, & May, 2000; Chen & Bliese, 2002; Walumbwa, Lawler, Avolio, Wang, & Shi, 2005) self-efficacy and leader accountability. For self-efficacy is supported by ideas and research to become a spiritual field and thus open to growth (Bandura, 2000; Karl, O'LearyKelly and Martocchio, 1993; Luthans, 2002; Maddux, 2002; Martocchio, 1994; Martocchio & Judge, 1997; Strajkovic & Luthans, 1998), Avolio & Walumbwa (2006), suggest that leaders can play an important role in increasing individual performance and ultimately overall performance over time. Similarly, research by Muppithathi & Krishnan (2015) revealed that leaders have an impact on the collective effectiveness of followers.

Furthermore, the researcher has not come across a study that dealt with the mediating influence of leader accountability on the relationship between the transcendental leadership of school heads and teacher self-efficacy in the local setting. It is on this context that the researcher is motivated to decide whether leader accountability has a mediating influence on the relationship between the transcendental leadership of school heads and self-efficacy of teachers who are teaching at the high school level at Davao Oriental, as this may concern the beneficiaries targeted by this study and possibly develop action plans to improve school leadership accountability as self-transcendent and effective leadership leaders and teachers. It is therefore imperative to conduct this study.

1.1. Research Questions:

The main thrust of the study is to find out the significance of the mediation of leader accountability on the relationship between the transcendental leadership of school heads and the self-efficacy of secondary teachers teaching in Davao Oriental. Moreover, it has the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of transcendental leadership of school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 Vision, hope and faith,
 - 1.2 Dedication, and
 - 1.3 The leader and follower spiritual development.
2. To ascertain the level of teacher self-efficacy in terms of:
 - 2.1 Classroom context, and
 - 2.2 School context.
3. To describe the level of leader accountability of school heads
4. To determine the significance of the relationship between:
 - 4.1 leader accountability and transcendental leadership;
 - 4.2 leader accountability and teacher self-efficacy; and
 - 4.3 transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy.
5. To determine the significance of the mediation of leader accountability on the relationship between the transcendental leadership of school heads and teacher self-efficacy.

1.2. Theoretical Framework

The foundation for this research is the Social Cognitive Theory of Bandura (1986). A large body of empirical research backs up social cognitive theory as a conceptual framework for human functioning. The evidence for the reliability of the social cognitive theory, according to Locke (1991), is very strong (p.293). As a result, leadership researchers and practitioners can rely on its concepts and principles. Its theoretical utility is demonstrated by the fact that it can be used as

the theoretical foundation for a leadership model that can explain why self-confidence typically correlates with different measures of leader effectiveness. According to the social cognitive model of leadership, managerial leaders who are confident in their leadership capabilities will choose higher aspirations and implement their talents and capabilities more efficaciously than those who are plagued by self-doubt.

The following points of view are offered to back up the above assertion:

Perry and McWilliam (2017) argued that school principals should be held accountable for all school policies and procedures to everyone who expect schools to succeed in quantifiable and visible ways. In addition, principals' ability to lead schools to success may benefit the global educational platform in identifying effective school reform and accountability strategies (Santamaria, 2014). Similarly, according to Rebores (2019), administrators who experience a sense of transcendence can focus on the tasks and responsibilities of their leadership roles within a specific school while simultaneously thinking about their larger objectives for being educational leaders. Furthermore, according to Zohar and Marshall (2018), management is essential in understanding, influencing, and sustaining organization behavior because they are able to prioritize and establish innovation among employees in the organization, which is often reflected in employee beliefs, attitudes, and behavior, which represent needs and motivations. Leaders who want to teach their followers on a mental, emotional, and spiritual level must first master the combination of their IQ, EQ, and SQ (Shabnam & Tung, 2012).

1.3 Conceptual Framework

The independent variable, dependent variable, and mediating variable of the study are shown in Figure 1's conceptual paradigm. The independent variable of the study is the transcendental leadership which has its indicators: *vision, hope and faith; dedication;* and *the leader and follower spiritual development* (Sayadi et al., 2016). The dependent variable is the teacher self-efficacy which has the following indicators: *classroom context,* and *school context* (Friedman & Kass, 2002).

A mediating variable was used in this study. This variable is one that describes the association between the other two variables. It interprets the association between independent and dependent variables. Further, the mediating variable acts as an intermediary between independent and underlying factors and a final outcome. Its goal is to determine how a variable influences the effect of X on Y. The outcome is considered to be caused by the mediator, not the other way around. One motivation for evaluating mediation is to identify the method through which the original variable effects the outcome (Baron & Kenny, 1986). In this present study, the mediating variable is leader accountability which has its indicators: responsibility, openness, and answerability (Wood & Winston, 2002).

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study

2. METHOD

This study employed a correlational approach and a quantitative, non-experimental research design. A correlational approach is a non-experimental design in which the researcher explores the link between two or more variables in an uncontrolled natural situation. Researchers look at how a change in one variable is associated with a change in the other variable in correlational studies to see how strong the correlations between variables are (Cresswell, 2013).

The mediation model aims to discover and explain the mechanism or process that underpins an observed connection between an independent variable (transcendental leadership) and a dependent variable (teacher self-efficacy) via the inclusion of a third explanatory variable, known as a mediator variable (leader accountability). A mediational model proposes that the independent variable impacts the mediator variable, which effects the dependent variable. In other words, mediating interactions exist when a third variable is significant in determining the relationship between the other two variables. (MacKinnon, 2008).

The questionnaire for transcendental leadership was adapted from Sayadi et al. (2016) it was modified to match the study's requirements and was subjected to expert approval. The following indicators are included in the transcendental leadership questionnaire: *vision, hope, and faith; dedication; and the leader and follower's spiritual development.*

In evaluating the transcendental leadership of school heads, the following five orderable gradations were employed, together with their associated ranges of means and descriptions:

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the items related to the transcendental leadership of school heads are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the items related to the transcendental leadership of school heads are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the items related to the transcendental leadership of school heads are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the items related to the transcendental leadership of school heads are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the items related to the transcendental leadership of school heads are not manifested at all.

Further, the questionnaire for teacher self-efficacy was adapted from Friedman and Kass (2002). It was changed to fit into the research and was subjected to expert evaluation. The following indicators were included in the questionnaire for teacher self-efficacy: *classroom context and school context.*

In evaluating the teacher self-efficacy, the following methods, along with their descriptions, were employed.

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the items related to teacher self-efficacy are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the items related to teacher self-efficacy are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the items related to teacher self-efficacy are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the items related to teacher self-efficacy are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the items related to teacher self-efficacy are not manifested at all.

Moreover, the leader accountability questionnaire was derived from Wood and Winston (2002). It was changed to fit into the research and will be subjected to expert evaluation. The following indicators are included in the leader accountability questionnaire: responsibility, openness, and answerability.

The following means and descriptions were used to evaluate the leader accountability of school principals.

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the items related to leader accountability of school heads are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the items related to leader accountability of school heads are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the items related to leader accountability of school heads are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the items related to leader accountability of school heads are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the items related to leader accountability of school heads are not manifested at all.

The research instrument's initial draft was given to the research adviser for comments, ideas, and recommendations to enhance its presentation, with the adjustments to be included and integrated. The final versions were sent to an expert group for review. The final draft incorporated the errors, comments, and recommendations provided by the expert validators prior to data collection. The experts' combined results yielded an average weighted mean of 3.97, which is described as very good verbally.

Furthermore, pilot testing of the research instrument was conducted on selected teachers who were not participants in the study prior to its administration. The internal consistency method was used to examine the reliability of the survey questionnaire for the pilot test. This is the best strategy to utilize because the test comprises dichotomously scored items in which the examinee either passes or fails. Using Cronbach's alpha, the instrument's dependability was calculated to be more than 0.7. This indicates that the tools utilized were trustworthy.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Level of Transcendental Leadership of School Head

The level of Transcendental Leadership of School Principals is shown in Table 1. The standard deviation was less than one, indicating that the replies were consistent. The mean score was 4.25 or very high. Distinctively, the level of transcendental leadership of school heads was measured using the following indicators: *vision, hope, and faith* have a mean of 4.49 described as *very high*, *dedication* has a mean of 4.38 with a descriptive level of *very high*, *the leader-follower spiritual constant development* has a mean of 4.47 characterized as *very high*, *altruism* has a mean of 4.33 described as *very high*, *chivalry* has a mean of 3.66 labeled as *high*, *politeness* has a mean of 4.49 characterized as *very high*, *civil characteristics* with a descriptive level of *very high* and *ethical issues* has a mean of 3.84 labeled as *high*.

Table 1: Level of Transcendental Leadership

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Vision, Hope, and Faith	0.594	4.49	Very High
Dedication	0.614	4.38	Very High
The Leader-Follower Spiritual Constant Development	0.587	4.47	Very High
Altruism	0.792	4.33	Very High
Chivalry	0.962	3.66	High
Politeness	0.769	4.36	Very High
Civil Characteristics	0.618	4.49	Very High
Ethical Issues	0.756	3.84	High
Overall	0.556	4.25	Very High

Data revealed that the school heads had always manifested transcendental leadership in terms of *vision, hope, and faith, dedication, the leader-follower spiritual constant development, altruism, chivalry, politeness, civil characteristics, and ethical issues*. This means that the school heads have *very high levels* in motivating their followers not only extrinsically and intrinsically, but also transcendently. More specifically, the level of transcendental leadership of school heads in terms of *vision, hope, and faith* was very high, indicating that the school heads always manifest and understand the vision of their organization and he/she is committed to that. Also, the data reflected a very high level of dedication which means that the school heads always manifest righteous and trustworthy behavior. In addition, the school heads attained very high levels of transcendental leadership in terms of the leader-follower spiritual constant development which indicates that the school head always manifests promotion of their own spiritual life. Furthermore, the level of altruism of the school head is very high, which means that they always help other people around them. Also, the school heads achieved a high level of transcendental leadership in terms of politeness which means that they always think about how behavior can influence duty. Moreover, their level of civil characteristics is also very high which is indicative of always manifesting awareness of the last changes in the organization.

On the other hand, the level of transcendental leadership of the school heads in terms of chivalry is high, which means that most of the time they manifest the discovery of problems that exist in the organization. Lastly, ethical issues also achieved a high level, which means that the school heads most of the time manifest an appearance which is higher than the usual and ordinary level.

3.2 Level of Teacher Self-Efficacy

The level of Transcendental Leadership of School Principals is shown in Table 1. The standard deviation was less than one, indicating that the replies were consistent. The mean score was 4.25 or very high. Distinctively, the level of transcendental leadership of school heads was measured using the following indicators: *vision, hope, and faith* have a mean of 4.49 described as *very high*, *dedication* has a mean of 4.38 with a descriptive level of *very high*, *the leader-follower spiritual constant development* has a mean of 4.47 characterized as *very high*, *altruism* has a mean of 4.33 described as *very high*, *chivalry* has a mean of 3.66 labeled as *high*, *politeness* has a mean of 4.49 characterized as *very high*, *civil characteristics* with a descriptive level of *very high* and *ethical issues* has a mean of 3.84 labeled as *high*.

Table 2: Level of Teacher Self-Efficacy

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Class Context	0.494	4.42	Very High
School Context	0.497	4.26	Very High
Overall	0.477	4.34	Very High

The table reflects the level of self-efficacy of teachers in terms of class and school context which is very high. This means that these teachers had better levels of work satisfaction, lower levels of job-related stress, and have fewer issues dealing with misbehavior among children. More specifically, their level of self-efficacy in terms of class context is very high which is indicative of always manifesting the ability to tie their teaching with their students' everyday interests and the ability to be creative in their work with students. Also, their self-efficacy in terms of school context had very high levels. This entails that these teachers always manifest a belief that they have a good relationship with the school administration and they actively involve themselves in crucial school decision-making processes.

3.3 Level of Leader Accountability

The level of Leader Accountability of Cateel and Baganga school heads is shown in Table 3. The overall mean score was 4.36, which was classified as very high. This suggests that the leader's accountability is constantly visible. When school leaders recognize positive work by individual team members and the overall group, it may be concluded that they are accountable and keep their employees accountable.

Table 3: Level of Leader Accountability

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
The leader is demonstrating a sense of obligation to constituents when making decisions	0.722	4.44	Very High
The leader is holding himself/herself to an accepted standard of performance	0.717	4.43	Very High

The leader is accepting responsibility for his/her actions within the organization	0.604	4.51	Very High
The leader is clearly defining for constituents where his/her responsibilities end and theirs begin	0.701	4.42	Very High
The leader is providing constituents with safe ways to address grievances against him/her	0.732	4.45	Very High
The leader avoids making excuses for mistakes	0.731	4.44	Very High
The leader is avoiding blaming others for mistakes	0.674	4.44	Very High
The leader is avoiding communicating an attitude of personal happiness	0.629	4.31	Very High
The leader is realistically reckoning with problems and challenges	0.605	4.39	Very High
The leader is wanting to know the truth, regardless of the consequences	0.655	4.46	Very High
The leader is willing to face the truth, even when it does not fit his/her personal preferences	0.680	4.38	Very High
The leader is accepting responsibility for the future direction and accomplishment of the group	0.626	4.50	Very High
The leader is accepting ownership for the results of his/her decisions and actions	0.665	4.26	Very High
The leader is accepting responsibility for the direction of the group he/she leads	0.735	4.25	Very High
The leader is looking to himself/herself first when the group's results is disappointing	0.746	4.28	Very High
The leader is striving to contribute as much as possible to the effectiveness of the organization	0.733	4.33	Very High
The leader is accepting responsibility for reaching organizational or team goals	0.641	4.49	Very High
The leader is accepting responsibility for the performance of the group he/she leads	0.585	4.59	Very High
The leader is fulfilling the commitments he/she makes to constituents	0.733	4.35	Very High
The leader's behavior is being consistent from one person to the next	0.755	4.38	Very High
The leader in delivering on his/her commitments	0.847	4.35	Very High
The leader is living out the values of the larger organization	0.877	4.37	Very High
The leader is demonstrating consistency in public and private behavior	0.756	4.42	Very High
The leader is identifying personal actions – popular or not – as his/her own	0.813	4.31	Very High
The leader is openly listening when people offer perspectives that are different from his/her own	0.814	4.33	Very High
The leader is choosing service above self-interest in the use of his or her power	0.640	4.46	Very High
The leader is overlooking personal advantage for the sake of the larger organization	0.663	4.42	Very High
The leader is avoiding isolating from constituents in performing his or her duties	0.693	4.43	Very High
The leader is “walking his/her talk”	1.040	4.08	High
The leader is openly explaining his/her decisions	1.031	4.14	High
The leader is openly declaring his/her values	0.862	4.33	Very High

The leader is living up to his/her stated values	0.814	4.37	Very High
The leader is communicating what he/she expects from constituents	0.822	4.35	Very High
The leader is openly sharing information about organizational resources with constituents	0.688	4.43	Very High
The leader is being a role model	0.598	4.50	Very High
The leader is behaving consistently from one situation to the next	0.702	4.39	Very High
The leader is acting tolerantly of those who disagree with him/her	0.673	4.39	Very High
The leader is submitting himself/herself to accepted evaluating/auditing processes	0.676	4.31	Very High
The leader is interacting openly and candidly with constituents	0.700	4.38	Very High
The leader is openly sharing his/her thoughts	0.641	4.51	Very High
The leader is explaining himself/herself to constituents in clear and understandable language	0.694	4.44	Very High
The leader is keeping records that are accessible to constituents	0.654	4.40	Very High
The leader is considering all relevant points of view	0.731	4.35	Very High
The leader is openly communicating about the progress of his/her commitments to constituents	0.790	4.25	Very High
The leader is apologizing to constituents for his/her mistakes	0.640	4.38	Very High
The leader is explaining the reasons for his/her decisions	0.689	4.39	Very High
The leader is explaining his/her beliefs to constituents	0.754	4.26	Very High
The leader is answering questions from constituents	0.714	4.30	Very High
The leader is providing explanations for the performance shortfalls without making excuses	0.749	4.21	Very High
The leader in providing detailed explanations of past actions and events	0.621	4.39	Very High
The leader is talking to constituents about the values of the larger organization	0.754	4.19	High
The leader is informing constituents of the process by which he/she arrives at decisions	0.665	4.33	Very High
The leader is explaining to constituents why suggested action was not taken	0.693	4.34	Very High
The leader is seeking regular feedback	0.675	4.41	Very High
The leader is providing regular progress reports about personal commitments he/she has made to constituents	0.737	4.35	Very High
The leader is welcoming constructive feedback of his/her actions	0.833	4.26	Very High
The leader is explaining reasons for standing behind his/her decisions	0.756	4.32	Very High
The leader is openly admitting his/her mistakes to constituents	0.748	4.27	Very High
The leader is taking quick action to deal with the consequences of a mistake	0.686	4.14	High
Overall	0.564	4.36	Very High

Leader accountability is also demonstrated when school leaders consistently deliver on their promises, demonstrating to others that they can be trusted to do what they say they will do. Leaders go even further by accepting responsibility for the outcomes of their activities and decisions and successfully transforming effort into results.

3.4 Significance of the Relationship between the Transcendental Leadership and Leader Accountability

The findings of the test of the association between transcendental leadership and leader accountability are shown in Table 4. The association was assessed at the 0.05 threshold of significance, as stated in the hypothesis. The total r-value of .702 with a p-value of 0.01 indicated that the null hypothesis was rejected. It implies that there is a strong link between transcendental leadership and leader accountability. This means that the school principal's transcendental leadership is linked to leader accountability. Distinctively, since the p-value is 0.01 and the total r-value is .795, the results show that all markers of transcendental leadership are positively connected on leader accountability on *vision, hope, and faith*, 0.634 on *dedication*, 0.757 on the *leader-follower spiritual constant development*, 0.680 on *altruism*, 0.212 on *chivalry*, 0.587 on *politeness*, 0.681 on *civil characteristics*, and 0.268 on *ethical issues*. Data show a positive association between the two variables.

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Transcendental Leadership and Leader Accountability

Transcendental Leadership	Leader Accountability Overall
Vision, Hope, and Faith	.795* (0.000)
Dedication	.634* (0.000)
The Leader-Follower Spiritual Constant Development	.757* (0.000)
Altruism	.680* (0.000)
Chivalry	.212* (0.000)
Politeness	.587* (0.000)
Civil Characteristics	.681* (0.000)
Ethical Issues	.268* (0.000)
Overall	.702* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

3.5 Significance of the Relationship between the Leader Accountability and Teacher Self-Efficacy

Reflected in Table 5 is the correlational analysis result between leader accountability and teacher self-efficacy. Results revealed that there is a significant relationship between the two variables with an overall p-value of 0.000. This means that as the level of leader accountability of school heads increases, the teachers' self-efficacy also increases. Moreover, the null hypothesis is also rejected since the overall p-value is below 0.05.

Specifically, the analysis revealed that all indicators of teacher self-efficacy have a significant relationship with leader accountability. The *class context* indicator posted a p-value of 0.000 with an r-value of 0.702. Also, the *school context* indicator has a p-value of 0.000 with an r-value of 0.639.

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Leader Accountability and Teacher Self-Efficacy

Leader Accountability	Teacher Self-Efficacy		
	Class Context	School Context	Overall
Overall	.702* (0.000)	.639* (0.000)	.696* (0.000)

Significant at 0.05 significance level.

3.6 Significance of the Relationship between the Transcendental Leadership and Teacher Self-Efficacy

The importance of the link between transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy is presented in Table 6. The total p-value of 0.000 indicates that there is a significant association between the two variables. Because the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is likewise rejected. This indicates that as the amount of teacher self-efficacy rises, so will the level of transcendental leadership.

When analyzed according to the indicators, results showed all indicators of both transcendental and teacher self-efficacy have positive significant results with an overall p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.790. More specifically results revealed that teacher self-efficacy has significant relationships with *vision, hope, and faith* with an r-value of 0.839, *dedication* with an r-value of 0.778, *the leader-follower spiritual constant development* with an r-value of 0.856, *altruism* with an r-value of 0.606, *chivalry* with an r-value of 0.345, *politeness* with an r-value of 0.642, *civil characteristics* with an r-value of 0.734, and *ethical issues* with an r-value of 0.368.

When transcendental leadership was correlated with the indicators of self-efficacy, results showed that there is a significant relationship in all the indicators with a p-value of 0.000 and an r-value of 0.790. In terms of *class context*, the r-value is 0.772. Also, in terms of *school context*, the r-value is 0.750.

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between the Transcendental Leadership and Teacher Self-Efficacy

Transcendental Leadership	Teacher Self-Efficacy		
	Class Context	School Context	Overall
Vision, Hope, and Faith	.834* (0.000)	.783* (0.000)	.839* (0.000)
Dedication	.785* (0.000)	.714* (0.000)	.778* (0.000)
The Leader-Follower Spiritual Constant Development	.859* (0.000)	.790* (0.000)	.856* (0.000)
Altruism	.605* (0.000)	.563* (0.000)	.606* (0.000)
Chivalry	.319* (0.000)	.344* (0.00)	.345* (0.000)
Politeness	.619* (0.000)	.619* (0.000)	.642* (0.000)
Civil Characteristics	.718* (0.000)	.697* (0.000)	.734* (0.000)
Ethical Issues	.332* (0.000)	.379* (0.000)	.368* (0.000)
Overall	.772* (0.000)	.750* (0.000)	.790* (0.000)

Significant at 0.05 significance level.

3.7 Mediating Effect

The regression study on the mediating effect of leader accountability on the connection between transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy is shown in Table 7. The information in this table was fed into the medgraph. There are three stages that must be completed before a third variable may operate as a mediator (Baron & Kenny, 1986). In Table 7 these are categorized as Steps 1 through 3. The fourth and last step is Transcendental leadership, as the independent variable (IV), strongly predicts teacher efficacy, the dependent variable, in Step 1 (Path c) (DV). Transcendental leadership (IV) substantially predicts leader responsibility in Step 2 (Path a), and the mediator (MV). In Step 3, leader accountability (MV) predicts transcendental leadership considerably. Step 4 involves combining transcendental leadership and leader accountability have a major impact on teacher self-efficacy.

Further mediation analysis using medgraph (Jose, 2003) is recommended for triangulation, with the Sobel Test used to determine the significance of the mediation effect. If the influence of the IV on the DV becomes non-significant at the end of the study, complete mediation is accomplished. This suggests that the mediating variable mediates all of the effects. If the regression coefficient is significantly lowered in the last stage but remains significant, only partial mediation is obtained. It indicates that portion of the IV is mediated by the MV, but the rest is either direct or mediated by variables not included in the model.

Table 7: Mediating Effect: Path Analysis (Significant Partial Mediation)

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
TL → LA	.712	.702	.042	17.042	***
LA → TSE	.237	.280	.040	5.938	***
TL → TSE	.509	.593	.040	12.595	***

3.8 Total, Direct and Indirect Effects

) is dramatically reduced in this scenario (leader accountability). As a result, only partial mediation occurred because the impact is still significant.

The inclusion of the mediating variable, leader accountability, significantly reduced the link between transcendental leadership (IV) and teacher self-efficacy (DV). The graph shows that 0.51 decreased to 0.08 in the subsequent regression. The 95 percent confidence interval proves that considerable mediation occurred. It produced a tiny standard error (se) of .040 when the lower limit (.4295) was subtracted from the upper limit (.5892) and the difference was divided by 3.92. (constant). The precision of the coefficient estimate is measured by the tiny se. The more exact the estimate, the less the standard error.

The impact size (.610) quantifies how much of the influence of transcendental leadership (IV) on teacher self-efficacy (DV) may be attributed to the indirect channel (IV to MV to DV). The overall impact (.6779) is the raw correlation between transcendental leadership (IV) and teacher self-efficacy (DV). The raw correlation between transcendental leadership (IV) and teacher self-efficacy is the overall impact (.6779). (DV). The magnitude of the correlation between transcendental leadership (IV) and teacher self-efficacy (DV) with leader accountability (MV) included in the regression is the direct impact (.5094). The indirect impact is the amount of the initial correlation between the IV and the DV that now passes through the mediator to the DV ($a*b$), where "a" denotes the path between the IV and the MV and "b" denotes the path between the MV and the DV. The ratio index is calculated by dividing the indirect effect by the overall effect, or $.1686 / .6779 = 25$ percent in this example. It appears that around 25% of the entire influence of the IV on the DV is mediated by the MV, and approximately 75% of the total effect is either direct or mediated by additional factors not included in the model.

The researcher confirmed that mediation is important and partial mediation exists by using Baron and Kenny's procedures in assessing the mediation of leader accountability. First, the independent variable (transcendental leadership) influenced the mediator (leader accountability) with a beta coefficient of 0.712, and the association is significant with a p-value of 0. Second, at a beta coefficient of 0.509, the independent variable (transcendental leadership) influenced the dependent variable (teacher self-efficacy), and the association is significant at a p-value of 0. Third, for the mediation to hold, the mediator (leader accountability) had an effect on the dependent variable (teacher self-efficacy) with a beta coefficient of 0.237 and the link is significant with a p-value of 0. Finally, both the independent variable (transcendental leadership) and the mediator are regressed on the dependent variable (teacher self-efficacy) (leader accountability). The partial mediation of leader responsibility on the link between transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy is achieved since the coefficient of transcendental leadership has been lowered but remains substantial.

After the enclosure of leader accountability as a result of the inclusion of a mediating variable in the multiple regressions, the direct relationship between transcendental leadership and leader accountability was lowered from 0.51 to 0.08. As a result, only partial mediation is achieved, given that the relationship between transcendental leadership and leader accountability remained substantial at $p < 0.01$, but went down from its initial value of .51. However, if the relationship between the two variables (transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy) is no longer significant or has gone to zero, complete mediation has been accomplished.

The total effect of (.6779) is the unadulterated relationship between transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy. The magnitude of the connection between transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy with leader accountability included in the regression is the direct effect of (.5094). The indirect effect of (.1686) is used to calculate the ratio index by dividing .1686 by the overall effect of .6779, yielding .25 or 25%. This means that 25% of the total effect of transcendental leadership on teacher self-efficacy goes through leader accountability and about 75% is a direct effect.

Because it is just partial mediation, it cannot be argued that leader accountability is the very reason how transcendental leadership can influence teacher self-efficacy. This indicates that leader accountability is merely one of the factors that contribute to how transcendental leadership can influence teacher self-efficacy.

Table 8: Total, Direct, and Indirect Effects

Effect	b	95% CI	
		Lower	Upper
Total	.6779	.6179	.7380
Direct	.5094	.4295	.5892
Indirect (mediation)	.1686	.1017	.2467

Figure 2. The Mediating Effect of Leader Accountability (LA) on the Relationship between Transcendental Leadership (TL) and Teacher Self-Efficacy (TSE)

*** Significant at

$$p < 0.001$$

4. DISCUSSION

The statistics on transcendental leadership, teacher self–efficacy, and leader accountability are discussed in this chapter.

4.1 Level of Transcendental Leadership

The level of transcendental leadership of school heads is *very high*, resulting from the very high and high levels of responses. The indicator with a very *high* level is *vision, hope and faith, dedication, the leader-follower spiritual constant development, altruism, politeness, and ethical issues*. The other indicators *chivalry and civil characteristics* have *high* ratings. The following indicators are presented from indicators with the highest to the lowest level.

The *very high level* result of the vision, hope and faith are indicative of the school heads understanding the vision of their organization and their commitment to that vision. Furthermore, they have faith in their organization and are ready to do anything to assure their organization achieves its aim. In addition, they contemplate some tough goals for their employment because of their confidence in the organization and its expectation of their accomplishment. Furthermore, their group effort has a goal for the best outcome for them. They also believe in the organization's vision for its employees. Finally, they strive to perform their best because they believe in the company and its leaders. (Sayadi, Habibi, & Savabeith, 2016).

The *very high level* result of *dedication* indicates that school heads support their members in the real sense and are having confidence in their teachers and staff and are being faithful to them. Furthermore, the school heads are being righteous and trustworthy. Also, the school heads are acting as they claim and they are kind to their teachers and personnel, and although they are struggling, they attempt to help them. Finally, the school heads are not punishing unintentional mistakes (Avolio and Locke, 2012).

The level of transcendental leadership in terms of *the leader-follower's spiritual constant development* is very high. This means that the school heads are paying special attention to their spiritual life and they are trying to promote it (Bolino and Turnley, 2012). Moreover, they have to pay great attention to teachers' spiritual life. Also, while someone's life is dedicated to a worthy cause, they are finding more value. Furthermore, the school heads are inspiring teachers to do something for others besides their own interests. Finally, the school heads are devoting themselves to serving higher aims (Fry, 2003).

Altruism gives transcendental leadership a very high level as well which means that school leaders are helping those with higher job loads. Also, they are always ready to help people who are around them and are helping eagerly those people who have problems in their work (Castro, Armario and Ruiz, 2004).

Chivalry, also an indicator of transcendental leadership, attains a high level. This entails that school heads are focusing on what is wrong and not paying attention and they are discovering that problems exist in their organization (Fry, 2015).

The very high result of politeness is an indicator that school heads are always thinking about how their behavior can influence their duty. Also, they are highly noticing the influence of their actions on other teachers and staff (Guenzi and Pelloni, 2004).

Civil characteristics attained a very high level. This means that school leaders are noticing all duties that they are not in charge of but they are being aware that this duty can help improve the general outlook for the organization (Lord and Brown, 2014). In addition, they are being aware of the last changes in their organization, are paying attention to the notice boards, and are adjusting themselves to them (Kamdar and Van Dyne, 2017).

Finally, ethical issues gained a high level which entails that the school heads in the organization are higher in ethics than the usual ordinary level. Also, the school heads are spending time resting (Maleki, 2009). Lastly, the school heads are always following the rule of the school even when nobody is looking at them.

4.2. Level of Teacher Self-Efficacy

Another aspect evaluated in this study is teacher self-efficacy, which is defined as very high. The *very high level* of teacher self-efficacy shows a very good command of the quality performance of the teacher. Very High level is based on the replies which are both at *very high* levels. The indicators are *class context* and *school context*. Teachers' self-efficacy, or their confidence in their capacity to effectively handle the responsibilities, obligations, and obstacles associated with their professional activity, is crucial in affecting critical academic outcomes such as students' achievement and motivation, as well as workplace well-being (Barni et al., 2019; Klassen et al., 2009; Klassen & Tze, 2014).

When teacher self-efficacy is analyzed according to the class context, it gained a very high level which means that teachers believe that their teaching has a good impact on the lives of their learners. Also, they feel that in their classroom, learners voluntarily comply with their teachers' requests and directions (Markoczy and Xin, 2014).

In terms of the school context, the teachers attained a very high level. This shows that teachers feel confident in their ability to make demands on the school administration and believe they can play a substantial role in addressing key school issues (Morghimi, 2015). Furthermore, these instructors say they have a positive relationship with their coworkers and a positive relationship with school leaders.

4.3. Level of Leader Accountability

Another variable considered in this study is *leader accountability* described as very *high*. The *high* level of *leader accountability* shows the very good command of the act of compliance with the rules and regulations of school governance. Moreover, the school head supervises all activities and programs conducted at the beginning level most of the time. This assumption is parallel with Halverson (2005) who pointed out that a good school leader manages so they get along well with their coworkers and get along well with school administrators and instill confidence in school stakeholders. School heads build an action plan with timelines to assigned responsibilities to enable the school vision to be accomplished. In short, there is a responsible implementation of the curriculum ideas and contemporary developments, staff development, fundamental parts of education, and supervision

Consequently, Strathern (2009) noted that schools are complicated organizations in which leaders must make choices and selections from a wide range of viable representations. These decisions are made within the restrictions and opportunities of the school's political and social milieu. They are influenced by the policy environment's objectives, restrictions, and climate both internal and external to the school.

4.4. Correlation between Transcendental Leadership and Teacher Self-Efficacy

The examination of the link between variables suggests that school leaders' transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy have a strong relationship. This suggests that the character of school leaders' transcendental leadership is linked to the school's qualitative performance. The examination of numerous authors' findings is supported by the findings of this study (Avolio et al, 2009; Bolam et al, 2005; Jue, 2004; Teegarden, 2006) who stated that transcendental leadership and teacher self – efficacy is a great predictor of leader accountability.

Moreover, effective leadership fosters a culture of continuous development in educational programs, teacher capacities, and student learning (Cossin & Caballero, 2013; Tshachenn-Moran & McMaster, 2009; Yukl, 2006). Consequently, transcendental leaders try to make changes that increase organizational efficiency and performance. School leaders matter for school success. (Avolio, 2005; Jones et al, 2008; Jue, 2004; Rubin et al, 2005; Weisberg et al, 2009).

4.5. Correlation between Transcendental Leadership and Leader Accountability

The test of the relationship between variables demonstrates a substantial link between transcendental leadership of school heads and leader accountability. This means that the level of leader accountability is associated with the nature of transcendental leadership of school heads. This agrees with the study of various authors (Lowder, 2011; Marshall, 2015; Zaccaro, 2007) who proposed that because addressing individual, campus-wide, and overall institutional needs is so comprehensive, school heads must be held accountable for the efficacy of service, programming, and financial utilization.

In addition, B.M. Bass and R. Bass (2008) stated that principals have a fundamental responsibility to ensure the overall achievement and motivation of the students, as well as the satisfaction and productivity of their faculty. Principals are able to affect the climate within their school through effective leadership and the modeling of values and beliefs important to education.

In a school setting, a head teacher has specific obligations, including being accountable for resource allocation and utilization, fostering effective teaching and learning, and encouraging the pursuit of continuous improvement. (Fullan, 2010; Teegarden, 2006). Teacher-researchers have stated that monitoring and assessing student success and teaching practices are critical components of school leadership, which is related to the notion of accountability within the professional learning community (Bolam et al, 2005; Marques, 2006, Jones et al, 2008).

4.6. Correlation between Leader Accountability and Teacher Self-Efficacy

The variable connection test demonstrates that there is a substantial association between leader accountability and teacher self-efficacy. This implies that that level of leader accountability is associated with the nature of teacher self-efficacy. The finding supports Fullan's study (2009) that accountability can lead to innovation necessary for greater school improvement if used intelligently. Annually, heads are held accountable to the governing body for their performance and attainment of personal goals. This is an improvement above prior systems for headteacher evaluation.

4.7. The Mediating Effect of Leader Accountability on the Relationship between Transcendental Leadership of School Heads and Teacher Self-Efficacy

The goal of this study was to add to the knowledge on indirect, mediating variables for the association between school leaders' transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy. While full mediation was not found in this study, significant and important direct effects were shown that may be of help in the enhancement of the existing research (Goker, 2006;

Runhaar et al, 2010; Tschannen-Moran and McMaster, 2009). Importantly, these authors' research on the relationship between transcendental leadership and self-efficacy consensus with Smith et al. (2003), who found that leader accountability can be used as a mediator to improve leadership skills, which have become critical to the creation and facilitation of effective teaching and learning environments toward a productive institution. In particular, the current study discovered that leader accountability is a positive and significant partial mediator of transcendental leadership and self-efficacy, matching the mediation requirements established by Baron and Kenny (1986).

The path between transcendental leadership and leader accountability, as well as the path between leader accountability and self-efficacy, were the subjects of the mediation analysis. The findings supported one of the study's framework explanations, by confirming the considerable association between transcendental leadership and leader responsibility of Santamaria (2014) who claimed that administrators' abilities to lead schools to success may help the global educational platform develop viable solutions for education reform and accountability measures. School heads play a pivotal role in developing the school climate required for success.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study validate the hypotheses concerning the mediating effect of leader accountability on the relationship between transcendental leadership of school heads and teacher self-efficacy (Smith et al., 2003). The data are regarded as widespread support of this concept. As a result, the findings show that considering transcendental leadership of school heads is significant for research on teacher self-efficacy, transcendental leadership, and leader accountability. The respondents agreed that the school heads' transcendental leadership has an impact on teacher self-efficacy. In practice, the respondents demonstrate a very high level of transcendental leadership, teacher self-efficacy, and leader accountability. It appears that there was a substantial association between school leaders' transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy. There was also a correlation between school leaders' transcendental leadership and their accountability as leaders. The influence of leader accountability on the relationship between transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy was partially mediated.

With the above-mentioned conclusions, the result of the study adheres to the Social Cognitive Theory of Bandura (1986). Self-confidence does, in fact, connect with several indicators of leadership performance. According to the social cognitive model of leadership, managers who are confident in their leadership abilities will set higher goals and deploy their talents and efforts more efficiently than those who are doubtful of their abilities.

6. RECOMMENDATION

A list of suggestions is made in consideration of the above results and conclusions. The very high level of transcendental leadership demonstrated by school heads, as well as the very high level of teacher self-efficacy and leader accountability, leads to the recommendation that school leaders may enhance their transcendental leadership and leader accountability for teacher self-efficacy. To sustain a very high level of transcendental leadership, school leaders may be provided with the opportunity by developing systems that will include all school leaders in training and seminars that will improve their management skills and teach them the significance of being accountable for the school's quality performance.

A high level of teacher self-efficacy indicates that the school is performing well, implying that learners are already benefiting from high-quality instruction, yet they still require ongoing development to facilitate the learning process. Educators should urge parents to be involved in their children's education. According to Witt Reich, Jacobi, and Hogue (2013), when parents and teachers work together, the bond between home and school intensifies. School instructors, administrators, parents, and students may collaborate because their connections are the foundation of successful teaching and student achievement (Witmer, 2005). Teachers may be introduced to trainings that help them encourage and engage their students as a medium for delivering classroom instruction that enables the interactive and collaborative learning process of the learners to achieve excellence. A high level of leader accountability indicates that school heads carry out their responsibilities as major actors in the school's functioning. It implies that Department of Education officials, teachers, students, parents, and community stakeholders may collaborate and recognize their different responsibilities in delivering excellent education, with a focus on developing leadership and accountability that makes the school productive.

The partial mediation of leader accountability on the relationship between transcendental leadership and teacher self-efficacy shows that school leaders should focus on school productivity and teacher efficacy while strengthening their administrative and supervisory roles. Finally, future studies aimed at exploring other variables that may have an impact on the relationship between the variables will be critical to the scientific community.

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